

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B039
 Date: 03 Aug 2004
 Take Off 08:33:46 13:27:02
 Landing: 11:47:00 17:36:54
 Flight Time 3h13m14 4h36m54

Trials Instructions: ITOP – Falcon Intercomparison
Operating Area: Horta – Porto - Cranfield

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Clare Reeves	UEA
4	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry/FWVS/CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
7	PERCA	Alex Parker	Leicester University
8	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
9	FAGE	Trevor Ingham	Leeds University
10	PAN/ORAC/WAS	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
11	AMS	Paul Williams	UMIST
12	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
13	Refuel engineer	Andrew Boardman	Avalon Aero
14	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
15			
16			
17			
18			

Track Plot:

B039 Track 03-AUG-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B039
 Date: 3rd August 2004
 Project: ITOP, return transit and Falcon intercomparison
 Location: Horta-Porto-Cranfield

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
083346		T/O	0.0 kft	204	From Horta
083910	084236	Run 1	7.0 kft	050	Wet chem checks
084353		Videos	9.2 kft	050	Start recording
085255	091625	Run 2	9.0 kft	118	Calibration Run
091626	093322	Profile 1	9.0 - 25.0 kft	084	
093435	110537	Run 3	25.0 kft	066	To BANAL
103305		Event 1	25.0 kft	090	Into light turbulence
103608		Event 1	25.0 kft	089	End of turbulence
111124	112819	Run 4	15.0 kft	093	Calibration Run
114700		Land	0.12 kft	170	At Porto
132702		T/O	0.12 kft	017	From Porto
133308		Videos	10.5 kft	023	Change tapes
133914	135933	Run 5	17.0 kft	021	Calibration Run
135942	140707	Profile 2	17.0 - 24.0 kft	049	
140707	144829	Run 6	24.0 kft	030	In broken cloud
1453		HORACE CRASH			

INTERCOMPARISON

151006	152646	Run 7	21.9 kft	283	With Falcon to QPR
153518	155408	Run 8	11.9 kft	110	Back to RIMON
160604	162710	Run 9	3.5 kft	359	Back to QPR
161820		HORACE CRASH			

Transit to Cranfield

163616	163950	Run 10	14.0 kft	359	Wet chem checks
165025	170349	Run 11	24.0 kft	359	
170359	171135	Profile 3	24.0 - 15.1 kft	037	1000fpm to FL160
170742		Videos	20.0 kft	035	Change tapes
171145	171643	Profile 3	14.8 - 6.1 kft	035	2000fpm
171712	172251	Run 12	6.0 - 5.0 kft	037	
172308	173149	Run 12	5.0 kft	054	descend to FL50
173654		Land	0.42 kft	355	At Cranfield

B039 Track 03-AUG-04

ITOP – Falcon Comparison

Mission Scientist: Claire Reeves

Date: 03/08/04

Outline schedule:

05:00 UT- Power to aircraft - Warm-up

07:45 UT – Security sweep

08:00 UT – Boarding deadline

08:30 UT- Take-off

Location: Horta -Porto- Cranfield

Aim: Fly to Porto intersecting polluted air from N. America and air of stratospheric influence. A filament of stratospherically influenced air is sandwiched between air of N. American origin. This is slanted upwards towards the east. Aim to intersect the lower level polluted air on route to BAVAS at about FL100. Ascend to FL240 before the main tongue of stratospherically influenced air into the weaker but higher level N. American pollution. En route to PORTO via BANAL cut into the stratospherically influenced air and back into the N. American filament below. From Porto rendez vous with the Falcon and perform 3 comparison runs between RIMON and QPR (not Queens Park Rangers, but Quimper). Then on to Cranfield may be intersecting air previously sampled by the 146 and the P3.

Note: 220 kts with exception of 210 kts for comparison.

Sortie Detail

- ✓1. Take Off. Ascend to first available level for wet chemistry checks.
- ✓2. Ascend to FL090 and transit to BAVAS (39N, 23 40W). Include at least 20 mins level in clear air for cals.
- ✓3. Profile ascend to FL250 at 1000ft/min.
- ✓4. Perform straight and level run to BANAL (42N 15W).
- ✓5. Descend to Porto (OPO, 41°14'53"N, 008°40'53"W) interrupting for a 20 mins at constant altitude for calibration purposes. *FL100*
- ✓6. Land at Porto (12:00 UT).

Ground power is required at Porto to keep instruments running and warm.

- 1345 Setcom call from Falcon.*
- ✓7. Take off 13:30 UT. Head towards SANTIAGO (42°55N, 08°25'W) and perform a run of least 20 mins at constant altitude (about FL100) in clear sky for calibration purposes.
 - ✓8. Ascend and transit to RIMON (45.5N 02W) (near Nantes) via LOTEE for rendez-vous at FL220 with Falcon at 15:15 UT .
Perform points 9-13 in formation with the Falcon at 220 kts.
 - ✓9. Perform a 15 minute run to QPR.
 - ✓10. Profile descend at 1000ft/min to FL120.
 - ✓11. Perform a 15 minute run back to RIMON.
 - ✓12. Profile descent to 3500ft (clouds permitting) at 1000ft/min above 5000ft and 500ft/min below.
 - ✓13. Perform a 15-20 minute run back to QPR.
 14. Transit to Cranfield to include a run at FL130 from Dawlish with 20 mins at the end for calibration purposes.
 15. Land at Cranfield (18:00 UT, 19:00 local).

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B039	DATE: 03/08/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 2
LOCATION: Horta – Porto – Cranfield		PROJECT: ITOP – Falcon Intercomparison	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	N2	Argon/CO2	CO
PRE FLIGHT	1240 psi / 86 bar	2010 psi / 140 bar	800 psi / 55 bar
POST FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)		
HORACE end of cal time:	ground	-	95.3	56.12	5371.91	130.208	37	0.03	0.21	0.23	-		
	Flow Lamp:	34.05	Press Monocr	0.97	Press Cell:	7.16	Press Cal Gas	2.66	Lamp °C	46.03	Monocr °C	22.35	PMT °C
06:54:14	Remarks: CO inst time set to HORACE time @ 06:45:00. All cal times taken from instrument Last cal time screen. Air sample pipe open.												
07:37:53	ground	-	100.88	57.08	5758.87	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks: Air sample pipe open.													
08:05:19	ground	-	102.29	57.09	5840.09	129.559	35	-0.02	0.27	0.25	-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks: Air sample pipe open. Max values of CO cal are 20-30 too high (535ppb-545) so another cal required.													
08:10:03	Ground	-	102.21	57.53	5880.38	154.238	32	5.71	5.28	10.99	-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks: Air sample pipe open. Top of cal 526 – 1ppb out. Much better.													
08:31:	taxiing	-	101.47	58.34	5919.35	213.219	35	1.23	5.39	6.61	-		
	Flow Lamp:	33.88	Press Monocr	0.97	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.65	Lamp °C	47.99	Monocr °C	22.02	PMT °C
Remarks: Air sample pipe closed. Post power changeover reboot cal.													
08:43:58	FL050	R1	100.45	57.55	5780.86		63	0.04	0.16	0.20	-		
	Flow Lamp:	34.09	Press Monocr	0.92	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.63	Lamp °C	48.70	Monocr °C	23.23	PMT °C
Remarks: Air sample pipe open. Cal ran over end of run and into climb at 08:42:36 – end of wet chem. tests – so probably an invalid calibration.													
08:56:19	FL090	R2	99.36	57.68	5730.99	88.632	61	-0.0	0.19	0.18	-		
	Flow Lamp:	34.00	Press Monocr	0.93	Press Cell:	7.16	Press Cal Gas	2.67	Lamp °C	49.19	Monocr °C	23.38	PMT °C
Remarks: Air sample pipe open. 08:52:55 start time for cal & run. CO cal peak readings 517-521.													
09:37:57:	FL250	R3	97.93	56.82	5564.49	91.548	57	-0.0	0.28	0.27	-		
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.80	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.59	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	23.57	PMT °C
Remarks: CO peak 515-518. TECO NOX cal started near end of CO cal.													
11:17:50	FL150	R4	104.07	54.56	5658.34	125.526	60	0.14	0.06	0.20	-		
	Flow Lamp:	33.96	Press Monocr	0.89	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.65	Lamp °C	47.32	Monocr °C	22.69	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal peak values 556-561													
11:23:20	FL150	R4	104.20	54.31	5658.94	116.960	60	-0.07	0.17	0.09	-		
	Flow Lamp:	34.05	Press Monocr	0.88	Press Cell:	7.11	Press Cal Gas	2.65	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks: 2 nd cal req to check CO gas peak level. CO peak level now 524-527.													
12:06:53	Ground	-	102.71	56.93	5844.52	163.129	-	-	-	-	-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks: Reboot due to switch to ground power @ 12:00:03													
13:13:56	ground	-	101.52	56.80	5766.20	158.728	12	32.2	41.5	73.7	-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks:													
13:22:21	ground	-	100.29	57.85	5802.41	126.642	24	3.85	6.08	10.42	-		
	Flow Lamp:	34.21	Press Monocr	0.93	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.68	Lamp °C	49.10	Monocr °C	23.40	PMT °C
Remarks: Power lost to CO on switch back to aircraft power @ 13:17:40. Air Sample pipe closed.													
13:45:18	FL170	R5	97.96	57.01	5584.32	111.750	62	0.01	0.17	0.18	-		
	Flow Lamp:	34.01	Press Monocr	0.86	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.63	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	23.77	PMT °C
Remarks: CO peak cal level: 510-513													
14:11:43	FL240	R6	97.07	56.51	5485.73	98.222					-		
	Remarks: CO peak cal level:519-522												
15:13:34	FL220	R7	101.11	54.70	5530.97	100.748	70	-0.09	0.24	0.15	-		
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.83	Press Cell:	7.16	Press Cal Gas	2.61	Lamp °C	48.73	Monocr °C	23.07	PMT °C
Remarks: 1 st comparison run. CO peak cal level:547-549													
15:38:44	FL120	R8	102.55	54.83	5622.79	99.483	53	-0.19	0.22	0.04	-		
	Remarks: CO peak cal level: 532-535												

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B039		DATE: 03/08/2004		OPERATOR: Doug Anderson					PAGE: 2 of 2		
LOCATION: Horta – Porto – Cranfield				PROJECT: ITOP – Falcon Intercomparison							
16:08:04	FL350	R9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Remarks: O3 values noted during HORACE crash/reboot as data is not logged internally on the instrument. See values below.											
16:10:51	FL350	R9	103.64	54.72	5671.51	92.003	39	-0.08	0.14	0.07	-
Remarks: O3 values noted during HORACE crash/reboot as data is not logged internally on the instrument. See values below.											
16:19:08	FL350	R9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Remarks: O3 values noted during HORACE crash/reboot as data is not logged internally on the instrument. See values below.											
17:21:39	FL060	R12	102.55	54.82	5621.93	100.427	45	-0.0	0.09	0.09	-
Remarks: CO peak cal level: 518-522											

TIME (UTC)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	O3 ()
16:08:04	FL035	R9	38
16:08:08	FL035	R9	38
16:08:12	FL035	R9	39
16:08:16	FL035	R9	38
16:08:20	FL035	R9	39
16:08:24	FL035	R9	38
16:08:28	FL035	R9	40
16:08:32	FL035	R9	39
16:08:36	FL035	R9	39
16:08:40	FL035	R9	39
16:08:44	FL035	R9	39
16:08:48	FL035	R9	41
16:08:52	FL035	R9	40
16:08:56	FL035	R9	40
16:09:00	FL035	R9	41
16:09:04	FL035	R9	40
16:09:08	FL035	R9	39
16:09:12	FL035	R9	38
16:09:16	FL035	R9	38
16:09:20	FL035	R9	37
16:09:24	FL035	R9	37
16:09:28	FL035	R9	37
16:09:32	FL035	R9	36
16:09:36	FL035	R9	37
16:09:40	FL035	R9	38
16:09:44	FL035	R9	39
16:09:48	FL035	R9	38
16:09:52	FL035	R9	37
16:09:56	FL035	R9	35
16:10:00	FL035	R9	36
16:10:04	FL035	R9	36
16:10:08	FL035	R9	36
16:10:12	FL035	R9	36
16:10:16	FL035	R9	38
16:10:20	FL035	R9	40
16:10:24	FL035	R9	42
16:10:28	FL035	R9	42
16:10:32	FL035	R9	41
16:10:36	FL035	R9	41
16:10:40	FL035	R9	39

TIME (UTC)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	O3 ()
16:10:44	FL035	R9	35
16:10:48	FL035	R9	35
16:10:52	FL035	R9	35
16:10:56	FL035	R9	36
16:11:00	FL035	R9	37
16:11:04	FL035	R9	35
16:11:06	FL035	R9	32
16:11:10	FL035	R9	33
16:11:14	FL035	R9	34
16:11:18	FL035	R9	34
16:11:22	FL035	R9	34
16:11:26	FL035	R9	33
16:11:30	FL035	R9	32
16:11:34	HORACE BACK		32
16:19:08	FL035	R9	42
16:19:12	FL035	R9	42
16:19:16	FL035	R9	42
16:19:20	FL035	R9	40
16:19:24	FL035	R9	40
16:19:28	FL035	R9	41
16:19:32	FL035	R9	42
16:19:36	FL035	R9	42
16:19:40	FL035	R9	43
16:19:44	FL035	R9	44
16:19:48	FL035	R9	45
16:19:52	FL035	R9	46
16:19:56	FL035	R9	47
16:20:00	FL035	R9	47
16:20:04	FL035	R9	47
16:20:08	FL035	R9	47
16:20:12	FL035	R9	46
16:20:16	FL035	R9	46
16:20:20	FL035	R9	46
16:20:24	FL035	R9	48
16:20:28	FL035	R9	47
16:20:32	FL035	R9	46
16:20:36	FL035	R9	45
16:20:40	FL035	R9	45
16:20:44	FL035	R9	46

TIME (UTC)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	O3 ()
16:20:48	FL035	R9	46
16:20:52	FL035	R9	47
16:20:56	FL035	R9	47
16:21:00	FL035	R9	47
16:21:04	FL035	R9	47
16:21:08	FL035	R9	45
16:21:12	FL035	R9	45
16:21:16	FL035	R9	45
16:21:20	FL035	R9	45
16:21:24	FL035	R9	46
16:21:28	FL035	R9	47
16:21:32	FL035	R9	47
16:21:36	FL035	R9	47
16:21:40	FL035	R9	47
16:21:44	FL035	R9	46
16:21:48	FL035	R9	45
16:21:52	FL035	R9	47
16:21:56	FL035	R9	48
16:22:00	FL035	R9	47
16:22:04	FL035	R9	45
16:22:08	FL035	R9	47
16:22:12	FL035	R9	47
16:22:16	FL035	R9	46
16:22:20	FL035	R9	47
16:22:24	FL035	R9	47
16:22:28	FL035	R9	49
16:22:32	FL035	R9	50
16:22:36	FL035	R9	49
16:22:40	FL035	R9	49
16:22:44	FL035	R9	49
16:22:48	FL035	R9	49
16:22:52	FL035	R9	49
16:22:56	FL035	R9	49
16:23:00	FL035	R9	49
16:23:04	FL035	R9	49
16:23:08	FL035	R9	48
16:23:12	FL035	R9	47
16:23:16	FL035	R9	47
16:23:20	FL035	R9	48
16:23:24	FL035	R9	48
16:23:28	HORACE BACK		47

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B..039.....

Date3.8.04.....

Page1..... of2.....

Video Tapes		GPS	INU	DRS ☒
V8		Lat	38° 31.26N	38° 31.26N
No.	FFC + loop	Long	28° 42.98W	28° 43.00W
Ends		Time	06:50:50	06:52:31
(FFC) / RFC / DFC / UFC		Status	✓	ALIGN
				HORACE ☒
				SATCOM ☒

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
080908	INU to	NAVIGATE	mode		Flight Plan	Horta	→ Porto	rejected.... waiting for clearance
083346	TAKE OFF	FROM	HORTA					
091251	Power readings		28V	0.7kVA	230V:	10kVA		
			ΦA:	20A	ΦB:	20A	ΦC:	17A
			Gen1	48A	Gen2:	50A		0952
								1056wx
093329	End P1	Display	locked	up.				
093435	start Run 3	est	BANAR	at 1040	, DIDIT	1114		
104600	Into	light	turbulence	again				10
			(ETA	1150)	At	Porto - ring	PC with	ATA
114700	LAND	AT	PORTO.	(3h 10)	GPS	Pos	Position	
					41° 14.08N		008° 40.95W.	
132702	TAKE OFF	FROM	PORTO					
						port / list		133202
								1500@Rimon
135612	PSAP	Pump	OFF	↓ Pump	ON	140644		
141010	"	"	OFF ↓	141340				
145227			145125					
1453	HORACE	crash						
1	RUN	8 ends						
160604	RUN	9 start	3500ft	161820	HORACE	crash		
162710	RUN 9	END						
163616	RUN	10	Wet chem	FL140				
163950	end	Run 10						
165025	RUN	11 start	FL240					
	FL70	-						1750

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3035 308 ozone g.chen@larc.nasa.gov

Gen

3039 → Clwé.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B.039**.....

Date**3.8.04**.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS			FFSSP		
Satcom C			PCASP		
Satcom H		✓	2D-P		
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C		
De-Iced Temp			Cloudscope		
Non De-Iced			SID 1		
Heimann		✓	SID 2		
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI		
G. Eastern			HVPS		
J. Williams			<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov	x		INC		
TWC			CCN / CNC		FWVS only
FWVS		✓	CVI		
<u>Radiometers</u>			<u>Aerosol</u>		
Upper Clear			PSAP		✓
" Red			Nephelometer	x	
" Silicon		JN02	AMS		✓
" JO1D		✓			
Lower Clear					
" Red					
" Silicon		JN02			
" JO1D		✓			
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS					
MARSS					
DEIMOS					
ARIES					
SWS / SHIM					
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone					
ECGC					
NOX					
CO			<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC					
PAN					
PERCA					
WAS		✓			

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B039 3.8.04

Instruments

1. Rear Facing Camera - no picture
 2. Signal Register not working for Heumann channel.
 3. All TWC channels to 65535 on power changeover. Switch off source and TWC then on, then okay, same again on landing at Porto
 4. Upper chr read - 107 W/m² after t/o
 5. FM display locked up, could not clear. Rebooted pc, then okay.
0933.
 6. UFC - thread or similar apparent on picture in flight, fluttering in the breeze!
 7. Turb Probe - check only Paras 599 and 600, 601 Turb P. Dry TAS, Wet TAS and corrected Pitot-Static all = 0 on HORACE, raw paras okay.
 8. TWC - status light flashing on approach to Porto 1140 ish + Cranfield
Para 72 - Sample Temp reading 608 (limits 640 → 1860)
Para 71 - TNOS = 1261 DRSV (limits 2000 → 3460)
Para 78 - Status = 4088
Sw Probe + heaters OFF. Restart, then okay.
HORACE crashed @ 1453
HORACE crash 160605 and 161820 both times when clicking OK on Update FITsum
- Error signature Appname iexplor.exe AppVer 6.0.2600.0 ModName: msjava.dll
ModVer 5.0.3502.0 Offset 00001932
- FM display - got into a loop of iexplorer errors - Got some SnagIt print
- HORACE crash after landing @ Cranfield 173930.

Aircraft